

Women's Experiences of Sexual Violence in India: A Field Study in Kurukshetra, Haryana

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This study investigated the consequential factors affecting the failure to curb sexual offences against women, irrespective of women's economic, social, and educational empowerment on sexual offences. The study was conducted in the Kurukshetra district of northeastern Haryana, India. A questionnaire consisting of 38 items for professionals in the field of law and enforcement and 39 items for the general public was used to collect responses. The survey received the highest number of responses from students (72%) and lawyers/advocates (45%). The survey reveals significant barriers to justice for victims of various sexual offences, including power, fear, and administrative failure. Workplaces, educational institutions, and automobiles were the most frequently reported locations for sexual harassment. Among the general population and professionals, 46.11% and 46.46% feared societal stigma, respectively, while 46.82% and 42.37% feared the harasser's retaliation when complaining about the ordeal. The study reveals significant barriers to access to justice. Additionally, 41.64% of professionals responded that inappropriate physical contact and online harassment were common. After reporting harassment, only 17.18% of the general population and 17.84% of professionals expressed satisfaction with the response given by the authorities. It is also being suggested that sexual offences are frequently perpetrated by members of the victim's professional or social networks, which makes reporting them even more challenging because of power disparities and peer pressure.

Keywords: Sexual offences, women, NCRB, law enforcement, Haryana, survey

Violence against women is one of the key social mechanisms that force women into a subordinate position in comparison to men. It is a manifestation of historically asymmetrical power relations between men and women, which have resulted in men's dominance over and discrimination against women as well as the prevention of women's complete advancement (United Nations, 2015). Crime against women occurs every three minutes, according to the National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) report (Maity & Das, 2024). The International Men and Gender Equality survey (2010) found that 65% of Indian men think women should put up with violence to maintain family unity and that women occasionally deserve to be beaten (Barker et al., 2011). In developing nations with high percentages of impoverished and disenfranchised populations, factors influencing crime against women (CAW) take on new dimensions. Thus, it would be intriguing to understand the

challenges that a country like India faces. The world's highest number of impoverished people resides here (Sumner et al., 2012), where the Human Development Index, female literacy, and female paid workforce participation are significantly below global levels (Drèze & Sen, 2012). It is widely acknowledged that "under-reporting by women survivors and under-recording by state agencies" has been one of the main issues in CAW (Pickup et al., 2001). It is well known that reported crime rates in India are lower than actual (Deosthali et al., 2022). Women of all races, ages, ethnicities, and socioeconomic backgrounds are impacted by violence against them. A startling range of behaviours, including rape, child marriage, female circumcision, and domestic abuse, are examples of violence against women (Bhattacharyya et al., 2022). These concerns have all spurred us to reexamine the geographic distribution and contributing factors of sexual offences against women in Kurukshetra (India). CAW is a worldwide concern. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030 are meant to be accomplished by 2030 by all UN member nations. Aiming for gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls, Goal 5 specifically mentions CAW. However, achieving several other SDGs, including enhancing health and well-being (Goal 3), acknowledging the significance of human rights (Goal 5), granting equal opportunity (Goal 8), and minimizing all forms of inequality (Goal 10), depends on ending CAW (Lolayekar et al., 2022).

This article aims to comprehend the consequential factors affecting the failure to curb sexual offences against women, irrespective of women's economic, social, and educational empowerment on CAW. To achieve these objectives, data were collected using a structured questionnaire, allowing for both qualitative and quantitative analysis of this issue.

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Purpose of the Study

The sexual offences against women in the Kurukshetra district of Haryana were examined in this study. The aim of the study is to use comparative methodology. The general people, embodying community-level experiences, were included, while professionals such as police officers, social workers, educators, and legal practitioners contributed informed viewpoints.

Hypothesis of the study

According to the overall goal of the present study, the following hypotheses have been developed in this context: *Hypothesis: Irrespective of the empowerment of women, the crime against women is on the increase.*

Method

Participants

The study was conducted in the Kurukshetra district of northeastern Haryana, India. The study area encompasses both urban and rural areas. Samples were selected randomly from January to October 2025. The local population (425), with 132 males and 293 females, and legal experts (269), with 159 males and 110 females aged 18 to 65, including police, judges, advocates, and law professors, provided the data. The sampling matrix was determined by demographic distribution, accessibility, and relevance to the study objectives, and the investigation was conducted in the Kurukshetra district.

Measure

The survey was titled "Attitudes about Sexual Crime against Women". Additionally, experts examined, discussed, accepted, or rejected questionnaire items using the Delphi technique, which involves a series of rounds, usually three, to obtain an agreement. A questionnaire comprising 38 items for professionals and 39 for the general public was used to collect responses. A 6-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 0 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*), was used to record the items.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the participants was tabulated. Appropriate statistical approaches were used per the study's goals and hypotheses. Quantitative data were analysed through SPSS version 21. The data was summarised using descriptive statistics such as percentages. Our analyses concentrate on the effects of violence indicators that women encounter.

Procedure

The data was collected through the questionnaire titled "Attitudes about Sexual Crime against Women" in both online and in-person formats, comprising 38 items for professionals and 39 for the general public. The questionnaire was both in Hindi and English.

Ethical Considerations

The fundamental ethical guidelines and accepted research procedures were used in the study. As necessary, the researcher made sure that potential informants could freely provide their informed consent to participate in the study and were informed that they might withdraw from it at any moment for any reason (Nusbaum et al., 2017).

Results

Socio-demographic Analysis

An overview of the professional, educational, and demographic characteristics of the two groups surveyed, the general public ($N=425$) and professionals ($N=269$), is given in Table 1. Legal awareness, gender, education, age, occupation, and residence are the main factors examined in this table. The majority of participants (79.40% of the general public) were between the ages of 18 and 35 years. On the other hand, only 63.94% of professionals were in the same age range (18-35), whereas 27.88% were between the age of 36 and 50. The largest percentage of participants were female, and the majority lived in urban locations. With 40.89% of professionals and 68.91% of the general population are female, and the survey demonstrates a good representation of women. Particularly in judicial and law enforcement jobs, this is essential for comprehending cultural perspectives and advocating for a gender-sensitive approach to justice. According to Table 1, the majority of participants from the general public (41.88%) and professionals (56.88%) also stated that their educational qualification is post-graduation.

Factors Responsible for Sexual Offences

The perceived causes of sexual offences among professionals and the general public are examined in Table 2. One of the table's most startling findings is the strong agreement on several factors that are thought to be significant causes of sexual offences. One of the most widely accepted causes was authorities' inaction; according to 78.12% of the general population and 73.23% of professionals, crime results from law enforcement and the judicial system's inaction. The impact of pornography is another widely accepted aspect; according to 75.09% of professionals and 76.71% of the general public, pornographic content influences deviant sexual behaviour. 71.29% and 74.35% of the public and professionals agree that an offender's mental state affects their criminal behaviour. Furthermore, 73.65% and 69.51% of professionals and the general public think that inadequate punishment encourages criminals and is responsible for ever-increasing sexual offences against women, indicating that harsher sanctions would be a more effective deterrent. The findings demonstrate a significant shift in societal attitudes, demonstrating that the behaviour or clothing of women does not primarily cause sexual violence. However, compared to 24% of the general population, 28.25% of professionals believed women pose more risks in public places at odd hours.

Challenges in Law Enforcement and Causes of Acquittals in Sexual Offence Cases

Police handling of sexual crime cases is examined in Table 3, which shows inefficiencies, delays, inappropriate evidence collecting, and outside influences. It sheds light on victims' access to justice and law enforcement's shortcomings. Both groups strongly agreed on police incompetence, which is one of the most concerning findings. According to 59.48% of professionals and 74.82% of the general public, delays in filing FIRs result in the denial of justice. Similarly, 65.06% of professionals and 82.11% of the general population felt that victims are frequently pressured to drop their cases, raising worries about pressure and intimidation from influential individuals. This indicates the need for more robust protection systems and a lack of trust in law enforcement since victims encounter societal and legal

obstacles while trying to obtain justice. There is a serious problem with the quality of police investigations; 73.88% of the public and 61.71% of professionals say that they are frequently improper, and 73.41% of the public and 64.31% of professionals say that victims and their families are being harassed during investigations. Furthermore, according to 61.33% of professionals and 78.11% of the general public, faulty evidence collection weakens cases and allows perpetrators to avoid punishment. According to the study, the leading causes of acquittals and the release of convicts include inadequate investigations, speed of disposal of cases, a dearth of evidence, and outside pressures. While 77.88% of the public and 60.22% of professionals concur that insufficient evidence frequently results in offenders being released, 75.52% of the general population and 65.06% of professionals think that inadequate or postponed investigations contribute to acquittals.

Patterns of Sexual Offences, Responses, and Barriers to Justice

The prevalence of sexual violence, victim responses, offenders, and reasons why victims do not disclose instances are all thoroughly examined in Tables 4, and 5. Many respondents had personally experienced or had known someone who experienced sexual violence. Sexual violence is a problem that many people encounter. Receiving unsolicited sexual messages or videos (36% of the general public, 50.55% of professionals), being followed, cornered, blocked or stalked sexually (30.59% of the general public, 30.86% of professionals), and unwanted touching (36.71% of the general public, 41.64% of professionals) are some of the most frequently reported forms of sexual violence.

According to the survey, most sexual violence was caused by males as per both the public (51.76) and professionals (52.79). Additionally, 79.92% of professionals reported sexual harassment by acquaintances, compared to 47.46% of the general public, indicating that most perpetrators were known people rather than strangers. Although sexual violence can happen in private and public spaces, some places are more susceptible than others. Workplaces (8.23% of the general public, 16.35% of professionals), educational institutions like schools, tuition classes, colleges or universities (23.52% of the general public, 32.34% of professionals), and automobiles (33.41% of the general public, 37.91% of professionals) were the most often reported locations by the general public and observed by professionals for sexual harassment cases.

Formal reporting is still minimal, even though sexual violence against women is a common problem. The fact that just 26.35% of the general population reported any such occurrences to the police suggests that people do not trust the legal system or law enforcement which is also supported by the fact that 42.38% of the professionals believe that such incidents were formally reported to police. The prevalence of confiding in friends (as per 38.12% of the general public, 37.92% of professionals) or family members (29.65% of the general public, 30.11% of professionals) was higher than the likelihood of taking legal action. In academic contexts, students are more inclined to report harassment, whereas working professionals could be afraid of reprisal or other professional repercussions. Fear continues to be one of the biggest obstacles to reporting sexual offences. In Table 5, the general public reported and professionals observed, 46.11% and 46.46% feared societal stigma, 45.17% and 44.60% feared parents and family, while 46.82% and 42.37% feared

Table 1

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

General public				Professional			
Variable	Description	Number (N=425)	Percent (%)	Variable	Description	Number (N=269)	Percent (%)
	Lack of awareness/training/ legal education on laws related to sexual offences against women in India	260	61		Lack of awareness/training/ legal education on laws related to sexual offences against women in India among the people	206	76.57
	Aware of the women's helpline no.	376	88.47		Lack of knowledge or awareness about women's helpline numbers among people	224	83.27
Age	18-35	337	79.40	Age	18-35	172	63.94
	36-50	62	14.70		36-50	75	27.88
	50-65	25	5.90		50-65	22	8.18
Gender	Male	132	31.09	Gender	Male	159	59.11
	Female	293	68.91		Female	110	40.89
Education	12th or below	42	9.88	Education	12th or below		0
	Graduation	133	31.29		Graduation	62	23.05
	Post Graduation	178	41.88		Post Graduation	153	56.88
	Higher studies	72	16.95		Higher studies	54	20.07
Professional status	Student	306	72	Professional status	Judge	8	2.97
	Government employee	44	10.35		Teacher	38	14.13
	Self-employed	22	5.18		Public Prosecutor	30	11.15
	Private employee	18	4.26		Police Officer	72	26.77
	Others	35	8.24		Lawyer/Advocate	121	44.98
Place of residence	Urban	233	54.82	Place of residence	Urban	155	57.62
	Rural	192	45.18		Rural	114	42.38

retaliation from the harasser. This supports the notion that victims frequently keep quiet out of fear of damage to their reputation, victim-blaming, or adverse community reaction. There is also a lack of trust in law enforcement, according to 34.20% of professionals and 27.52% of the general population who distrust the legal system.

Many victims are pushed into private remedies rather than pursuing legal justice, as evidenced by 76.57% of professionals and 78.85% of the general public mentioning out-of-court settlements as a factor for case acquittal. The study reveals significant barriers to justice for victims of sexual harassment, including power, fear, and systemic failure.

Table 2*Factors Responsible for the Incidents of Sexual Offences against Women*

Factors	General Public				Professional			
	Agree (N)	Strongly agree (N)	Number (N=425)	(%)	Agree (N)	Strongly agree (N)	Number (N=269)	(%)
Offender's mental status	172	131	303	71.29	112	88	200	74.35
Effect of Pornographic Websites	173	153	326	76.71	111	89	202	75.09
Failure to take proper action by the authorities	171	161	332	78.12	119	78	197	73.23
Insufficiency of harsh Punishment	149	174	313	73.65	106	81	187	69.51
Physically appealing dresses worn by women	71	32	103	24.47	45	23	68	25.27
Anti-feminist or Male-supremacist approach of offender	164	85	249	58.59	83	52	135	50.19
Increasing Independence of Women	70	22	92	21.65	44	16	60	22.30
Presence of women in the outside world during odd hours	75	27	102	24	55	21	76	28.25

Table 3*Defects in the Working of Police Authorities while Dealing with Cases, and the Causes of Acquittals/discharge of Offenders*

Factors	General Public				Professional				
	Agree (N)	Strongly agree (N)	Number (N=425)	(%)	Agree (N)	Strongly agree (N)	Number (N=269)	(%)	
Defects in the working of the police authorities	Delay in recording the FIR by the police	219	99	318	74.82	105	55	160	59.48
	Pursuing victim or her family to end the case	226	123	349	82.11	117	58	175	65.06
	Improper investigation by the Police	190	124	314	73.88	110	56	166	61.71
	Harassing the victim during the investigation	190	122	312	73.41	115	58	173	64.31
	Delay in the investigation by the Police	222	117	339	79.76	106	68	174	64.68
	Improper collection of evidence	209	123	332	78.11	97	68	165	61.33
	Influencing the witnesses to favour the offender	207	106	313	73.64	97	67	164	60.96
	Improper charge-sheet/ challan favouring accused	189	98	287	67.52	84	48	132	49.07
	Lack of knowledge of legal Procedures	196	109	305	71.76	99	53	152	56.51
	Improper charge-sheet/ challan favouring victim	173	87	260	61.76	87	53	140	52.04
Causes of acquittals/discharge	Shortage of female police personnel	194	97	291	68.47	76	66	142	52.78
	Improper, poor or delayed Investigation	214	107	321	75.52	99	76	175	65.06
	Long duration of cases affecting evidence	217	138	255	60	111	72	183	68.02
	Improper evidence/ Lack of Evidence	227	105	331	77.88	100	62	162	60.22
	Corrupt police officer/judicial officer/ advocate	182	136	319	75.05	82	68	150	55.76
	Witnesses changing their statements	219	120	339	79.76	122	76	198	73.60
	Pressure on the victim or her Family	180	171	351	82.58	107	81	188	69.89
	Out of court settlement among parties	202	133	335	78.85	132	74	206	76.57
Fake FIR/Complaint	161	89	250	58.82	85	51	136	50.56	

Table 4*Prevalence of Sexual Harassment among the Participants*

Experience of harassment (unwanted sexual way)	General public				Professional			
	Participant (N)	Someone known to Participant (N)	Number (N=425)	%	Participant	Someone known to participant	Number (N=269)	%
Someone pulled off clothes	32	54	86	20.23	20	40	60	22.30
Someone sends sexual messages/videos	82	71	153	36	65	71	136	50.55

Watched hiddenly while getting dressed/undressed	14	48	62	14.58	29	50	79	29.36
Watched hiddenly while using toilet/bathroom	17	38	55	12.94	27	42	69	25.65
Someone blocked way/ followed	62	68	130	30.59	37	46	83	30.86
Someone touched, grabbed or pinched	84	72	156	36.71	50	62	112	41.64
Someone came in close contact	70	55	125	29.41	42	52	94	34.94
Someone called or messaged repeatedly	95	75	170	40	60	66	126	46.84
Someone tried to take or actually took sexual advantage in relationship	34	57	91	21.41	38	50	88	32.71
Someone tried to kiss or kissed	46	48	94	22.11	33	48	81	30.11
Someone performed or tried to perform any other sexual activity	39	53	92	21.64	27	41	68	25.27

Table 5

Reason for Not Telling/reporting an Incident of Sexual Offence against Women

Reason	General public		Professional	
	Number (N=425)	%	Number (N=269)	%
Fear of revenge by the harasser	199	46.82	114	42.37
Fear of stigma	196	46.11	125	46.46
Fear of not being trusted or rather of being blamed	184	43.29	102	37.91
The harasser is/was in a position of power and influential	141	33.17	108	40.14
Considered the incident to be less serious	93	21.88	60	22.30
Distrust in the working of law agencies	117	27.52	92	34.20
Fear of parents/family	192	45.17	120	44.60
Did not want any action to be taken	54	12.70	53	19.70
Any other reason	84	19.76	74	27.50
Didn't want to ruin the person's life or harm their future	76	17.88	66	24.71
Fear of having no proof to support your claim	153	36	90	33.45

Discussion

The study found that sexual violence against women is prevalent in the Kurukshetra district of Haryana, India. Sexual offences are on the rise, according to both groups (public & professional surveys).

The findings of this study align with trends in sexual offences reported by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) report 2017-2022. The NCRB reports showed a steady increase in sexual offences over time, which is consistent with the prevalent belief among experts and the general public that sexual offences are on the rise nationally and regionally. Figure 2a shows the total number of reported cases of sexual offenses against women in Haryana and India continuously increased during the years 2017-2022. However, a small decline in cases was observed in the year 2020 may be due to lockdown circumstances during COVID-19 in India. Similarly, Figure 2b depicts the increased percentage share of cases reported in Haryana (out of the total reported cases in India) and Kurukshetra (out of the total reported cases in Haryana) during 2017-2022 (NCRB report 2017-2022). The percentage of reported cases increased from 2.8% to 4.1% in Haryana among the other states in India and 2.7% to 5.8% in Kurukshetra among the other districts in Haryana.

The graphs' (Fig. 2 & 3) primary finding is the year-over-year rise in reported instances of sexual offences against women (crime-head wise) under IPC, which may indicate that events or awareness is increasing. This is consistent with present research showing that

most respondents (both the general public & professionals) thought that sexual offences were increasing. The high rate of acquittals and legal delays is another significant trend that supports the worries expressed in earlier tables regarding the ineffectiveness of the legal system and law enforcement. The NCRB data, which reveals a discrepancy between reported cases and convictions, seems to support the survey respondents' complaints about the perceived notion that most of the cases of sexual assault against women end in acquittal, delays in justice, prolongation of investigation and inefficient legal action. As the NCRB report reveals, the overall conviction rate of crimes against women has been reported to be 25.3% in India and 13.2% in Haryana. Investigation of 23.9% rape cases, 25.6 % of assault cases, and 36.6 % of insult to the modesty cases in India were pending at the end of the year 2022 (NCRB report, 2022). The pendency percentage of 90% rape cases, 93% of assault cases, and 91% of insult to modesty cases at the end of the year 2022 in India has been noted (NCRB report, 2022). Overall, the data from the NCRB supports the main trends shown in the study, especially the increase in sexual offences, the public's mistrust of the police, and the call for harsher penalties.

Additionally, 79.92% of professionals reported harassment to the victim by acquaintances, compared to 47.46% of the general public, indicating that most perpetrators were known people rather than strangers. This suggests that sexual offences are frequently perpetrated by members of the victim's professional or social networks. According to the NCRB 2022 data, out of a total of 1787

rape cases in Haryana, offenders in 1753 cases were known to the victims which makes up to 98.10% share of known cases to total rape cases (NCRB report, 2022). A similar study conducted by Mathews et al. (2024) showed the prevalence of child sexual abuse (CSA) in Australia was 28.5%, with the following prevalences by classes of perpetrators: 10.0% for other known adolescents (non-romantic),

7.8% for parents/caregivers in the home, 7.5% for other known adults, 4.9% for unknown adults, 2.5% for adolescents (current or former romantic partners), 2.0% for institutional caregivers, 1.6% for siblings, and 1.4% for unknown adolescents. Except for institutional caretakers, women were more likely to experience CSA from all perpetrator classifications.

Figure 1

Total Reported Cases Sexual Offences against Women under IPC in Haryana and India and b) Percentage Distribution of Reported Cases under IPC in Kurukshetra and Haryana

Figure 2

Reported Women Sexual Harassment Cases a) India, b) Haryana, c) Kurukshetra

A study of individual perpetrator types revealed that known male adolescents, present and past partners, and fathers, male relatives living in the home, and non-resident male relatives all had higher CSAs, whereas other known male adults had lower CSAs (Mathews et al., 2024). Second, compared to young people in previous generations, young people now have easier access to pornography, including violent pornography. The exposure of adolescents to pornography in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar using UDAYA survey data from 2015-2016. The mean age was 16.66 years for boys and 16.67 years for girls. 47% of boys were exposed to pornography, while only 6% of girls were. The likelihood of exposure was higher among adolescents with personal mobile phones and frequent media exposure. The study recommends prioritising life skills and comprehensive sexuality education programs to reduce exposure to pornography among adolescents (Srivastava et al., 2023). The consumption of pornographic material may influence adolescent sexual aggression, and this tendency is increased when the content is violent. The adverse effects of violent pornography on sexual scripts and related cognitive schemas, attitudes, and behaviours-including

those related to negotiating consent-are in line with theoretical interpretations. Consuming pornography as a teenager, mainly when it is violent, can result in skewed sexual scripts that legitimise sexual coercion and abuse, increase the risk that it will occur in real life, and compromise the ability to give full, free, and voluntary consent for sexual engagement (Waterman et al., 2022; Rittenhour & Sauder, 2024). A similar trend for pornographic content use was also seen in the present study (according to 75.09% of professionals & 76.71% of the general public), where watching pornographic content influences deviant sexual behaviour.

In this study, it was found that sexual harassment via online mode is a prevalent issue, with 36% of the general public and 50.55% of professionals experiencing unwanted sexual messages or videos, 30.59% being followed or blocked sexually, and 41.64% unwanted touching. This trend escalates, requiring immediate attention to awareness efforts and cybercrime regulations. These results were inconsistent with many previous research examining online harassment. Powell et al. (2019) revealed that technology-facilitated sexual violence (TFSV) and harassment victimisation are prevalent

among Australian adults aged 18 to 54 years. Both men and women experience TFSV victimisation, with men reporting more nude images, unwanted sexual experiences, offensive comments, and virtual representations. They also report harassment or abuse from spam emails and pornographic advertising. Bennett et al. (2011) examined college students' experiences of electronic victimisation in friendships and dating relationships. 92% reported some victimisation, with males reporting more and females anticipating more distress. Both genders anticipated more distress in dating relationships. More experience reduced anticipated distress. The digital age has increased connectivity and remote employment, but it has also led to a rise in cyberattacks. Women are often targeted by cybercriminals and fraudsters, causing insecurity in cyberspace. This study uses statistical tools to understand the cybercrime trends against women in India. The analysis identifies vulnerable states and specific cybercrimes, including women. The study proposes robust guidelines for preventive measures to combat cybercrimes and improve the future (Sankhwar et al., 2024).

The high rate of harassment on public transit raises (33.41% of the general public, 37.91% of professionals) worries about women's safety when it comes to mobility, and the higher rate of harassment experienced by professionals at work implies that there are insufficient safeguards in place. According to the NCRB data, 422 total cases in India and 20 cases in Haryana were registered for crime in the public transport system (NCRB report, 2022). The factors influencing violence against women in public transport spaces were studied in a survey in Dar es Salaam City. The Data was collected through surveys, interviews, and documents. The findings reveal that women face physical, verbal, and sexual violence. The violence is influenced by cultural, legal, geographical, and economic factors. The study highlights the psychological, economic, health, and social effects of violence against women at public transport bus stations (Niboye, 2023). According to an analysis of the relationship between gender and transportation in low- and middle-income nations, women are afraid of the way public transportation places are designed in these nations (Uteng & Turner, 2019). Additionally, women cannot use public transportation at night due to inadequate lighting. More recently, it was shown that the layout of underground transportation facilities encourages aggression against women; as a result, female passengers are afraid of being harmed when they use the system during the day and after dark (Kim, 2021).

According to the survey, even thirty years after rape reform initiatives, college students still face obstacles when it comes to reporting rape and sexual assault. The biggest obstacles are shame, guilt, embarrassment, concerns about secrecy, and fear of being believed. While female victims fear reprisals from the offender, male victims fear being stigmatised as gay. Despite efforts to reform rape, these obstacles still exist (Sable et al., 2006). Another study examined the sociocultural hurdles to reporting, post-report societal reactions, and factors influencing male victims of domestic abuse. The findings indicate a favourable attitude toward reporting but hesitancy because of socio-religious status, livelihood loss, and stigmatisation fears. It is essential to recognise these situations for their safety, coping, and general well-being (Aborisade, 2024). Similar trends were also shown in the present study. Fear of societal stigma, retaliation, and reputational damage is a significant obstacle to reporting sexual offences, with 46.11% and 46.46% of the general public and professionals fearing such incidents, indicating a lack of openness.

In 2005, just six out of every hundred cases of sexual violence against women in India were reported to the police, indicating a high rate of underreporting. Less than 1% of occurrences were reported to the police, and survivors' spouses perpetrated most. This demonstrates the pervasiveness of structural violence against women in India and the difficulties women have when reporting such occurrences (Gupta, 2014). According to the survey, rape, kidnapping/abduction, and aiding and abetting suicide are among the worst crimes against women that have increased in India and Haryana. However, there have been cases of dowry death, murder, molestation, brutality to women, eve-teasing, and unethical trafficking. According to the report, there is a notable disparity between missing male and female children, and the leading causes include maltreatment, chain snatching, abduction, abetment to commit suicide, and unethical trafficking (Bijender & Kumar, 2023). Crimes against women in Indian society draw attention to how women are perceived concerning men, which shapes traditions and behaviours. In India, violence against women is a serious problem because women make up almost half of the population and frequently face discrimination from religious and sociocultural institutions.

This study in Kurukshetra district, Haryana, India, reveals a rise in women's sexual harassment, with a high rate of acquittals and legal delays. The prevalence of harassment is linked to pornography also, with adolescents' easy access to porn linked to increased risk behaviours. Online harassment is prevalent, with incidents involving unsolicited sexual content. Women face harassment on public transit and at work, with insufficient safeguards. Barriers to reporting sexual offences are primarily due to societal stigma and fear of retaliation. Despite government initiatives, a gap persists in crime reporting and handling, requiring more effective interventions.

Conclusion

This study examines sexual offences against women in the Kurukshetra district of Haryana. The socio-demographic analysis reveals that most participants were between 18 and 35, with a high representation of women in law enforcement and the legal field. The survey also revealed that 61% of participants had no training or legal education, and 88% were aware of women's helpline numbers among general public participants. The perceived causes of sexual offences among professionals and the general public are potent, with authorities' inaction being one of the most widely accepted causes. Factors such as police incompetence, victim protection concerns, delayed punishment, pornography, mental state, inadequate punishment, and misogynistic attitudes are also considered significant. Police handling of sexual crime cases is examined, showing inefficiencies, delays, inappropriate evidence collection, and outside influences. Both groups strongly agreed on police incompetence, with delays in filing FIRs leading to the denial of justice. Victims are frequently pressured to drop their cases, indicating the need for more robust protection systems and a lack of trust in law enforcement. Inadequate investigations, a dearth of evidence, and outside pressures are the leading causes of acquittals and dismissals of convicts. Out-of-court settlements are a significant problem in victim retaliation instances, underscoring the dearth of sufficient victim protection legislation and support networks. Sexual harassment, victim responses, and barriers to justice are also examined, with many respondents personally experiencing or

knowing someone who has experienced it. Formal reporting is still minimal, suggesting people do not trust the legal system or law enforcement.

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